

PEDAGOGICAL VIEWS OF EDUCATION SPECIALISTS. FACTORS AFFECTING YOUNG PEOPLE.

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Abstract. In this article, the spiritual and moral upbringing of children in the family, the formation of feelings of pride in the traditions and the important factors of providing excellent education and upbringing in education - the cooperation of the family, kindergarten, school and the neighborhood in education are highlighted.

Keywords: family, children, parents, neighborhood, Motherland, nation, people, religion, tradition, pride, love

Family is a socio-pedagogical group created to meet the needs of self-protection and self-esteem of each member. The family creates the concept of home in a person not as a room in which he lives, but as feelings and emotions that they expect, love, understand and protect. The family is such an upbringing that "embraces" a person in all its forms. All personal qualities can be formed in the family. The fateful importance of the family in the formation of an adult person is known to everyone.

Family education is a system of upbringing and education that develops with the efforts of parents and relatives in certain family conditions.

Family education is a complex system. This is influenced by the genetic and biological (natural) health of children and parents, material and economic support, social status, lifestyle, number of family members, place of residence, attitude towards the child. All these are interrelated and manifest differently in each case.

Family duties include:

- creating maximum conditions for the child's growth and development;
- becoming a child's social, economic and psychological protection;
- experience of creating and supporting a family, raising children and relationships with adults;
- teaching children useful skills and practical skills aimed at self-service and helping their loved ones;
- self-respect, education of self-worth.

Also, it is necessary to develop the effectiveness of the system of spiritual and moral upbringing of children in the family through the mechanism of cooperation of the family-preschool educational institution through the family. "Fundamentally improving the conditions in preschool educational institutions for the all-round intellectual, aesthetic and physical development of children, seriously increasing the coverage of children with preschool

education and ensuring its convenience, raising the level of qualifications of pedagogues and specialists"

The purpose of family education is to develop such personal qualities that help to overcome difficulties and obstacles encountered in life. Intellectual development and creative ability, initial work experience, moral-aesthetic formation, emotional culture and physical health of children, their happiness - all this depends on the family, parents, and all this is the task of family education. Parents are the first educators who have the strongest influence on children.

The importance of the influence of the family on the formation and development of the child's personality was clearly shown. Family and social education are closely related to each other, complement each other and can even replace each other in a certain scope, but they are not equal at all and cannot be so under any circumstances.

Family upbringing is more emotional than other upbringings, because its "guide" is the love of parents for children, which arouses mutual feelings of children towards parents. Consider the influence of the family on the child.

1. The family serves as the basis for a sense of security. Attachment relationships are important not only for the future development of relationships - their direct influence helps to reduce anxiety in a child in new or stressful situations. Thus, the family provides a basic sense of security, guarantees the child's safety when interacting with the outside world, learns new ways of learning and responding to it. In addition, loved ones are a source of comfort for the child in times of despair and anxiety.

Children tend to copy the behavior of other people and often those they are closest to. Partly it's a conscious attempt to behave like others, partly it's unconscious imitation, which is part of identifying with the other.

In this regard, it should be noted that children learn certain ways of their behavior from their parents not only by learning the rules (ready-made recipes) that are directly conveyed to them, but also by the parents' relationship. They also learn by observing existing patterns (eg. When the recipe and the example match, the child can behave like his parents.

3. The family is of great importance in acquiring the life experience of the child. The influence of parents is especially great, because they are a source of necessary life experience for a child. Children's fund of knowledge largely depends on how parents give the child the opportunity to study in libraries, visit museums and relax in nature. In addition, it is important to talk to children a lot.

Children whose life experiences include different situations and are able to overcome communication problems, enjoy different social relationships, adapt to new environments and respond positively to changes around them are better than other children.

4. The family is an important factor in the formation of discipline and behavior in a child. Parents influence a child's behavior by encouraging or condemning certain types of behavior, as well as by applying punishments or allowing them the degree of freedom in behavior that is acceptable to them. A child learns what to do and how to behave from parents.

5. Communication in the family becomes an example for the child. Communication in the family allows the child to develop his views, norms, relationships and ideas. A child's development depends on what good conditions are created for him to communicate in the family; development also depends on the clarity and clarity of communication in the family.

For a child, the family is the place of birth and the main place of residence. He has close people in his family who understand him and accept him as he is - healthy or sick, kind or not so good, obedient or rude and rude - he is his own.

It is in the family that the child receives the basics of knowledge about the world around him, and with the high cultural and educational potential of his parents, he continues to receive not only basic knowledge, but also culture throughout his life. Family is a certain moral and psychological climate, for a child it is the first school of relationships with people. It is in the family that a child's ideas about good and bad, manners, respect for material and spiritual values are formed. With close people in the family, he experiences feelings of love, friendship, duty, responsibility, justice...

Unlike public education, family education has certain characteristics. By its very nature, family education is based on emotions. Initially, the family, as a rule, is based on the feeling of love, which determines the moral environment of this social group, the style and tone of the relations of its members: gentleness, kindness, care, tolerance, generosity, the ability to forgive, duty feeling

A child who does not receive parental love grows up friendly, angry, rude to other people's experiences, rude, quarrelsome in the peer group, and sometimes closed, restless, extremely shy. A small person who grows up in an environment of excessive love, affection, respect and reverence will develop such qualities as selfishness, effeminacy, corruption, arrogance, and hypocrisy early on.

If there is no harmony of emotions in the family, then the development of the child in such families becomes complicated, and family education becomes an unfavorable factor in the formation of the individual.

Another feature of family upbringing is that the family is a social group of different ages: it includes representatives of two, three, sometimes four generations. And this means - different value directions, different criteria for evaluating life events, different ideals, points of view, beliefs. One person can be both an educator and a teacher: children - mothers, fathers - grandfathers - grandmothers and grandfathers. And despite these contradictions, all family members sit at the same dinner table, relax together, do housework, organize holidays, create certain traditions, and engage in the most diverse relationships.

As stated in Article 18 of the "Law on State Policy Regarding Youth" of the Republic of Uzbekistan, adopted on September 14, 2016: takes measures aimed at forming a spiritual and moral environment in the family.

A distinctive feature of family education is its inextricable connection with the whole life of a growing person: inclusion of the child in all life activities - intellectual and cognitive, labor, social, value-oriented, artistic and creative, playful, free communication. Moreover, it goes through all stages: from elementary attempts to the most complex forms of behavior of social and personal importance.

Family upbringing also has a wide range of influence: it continues throughout a person's life, happens at any time of the day, at any time of the year. A person experiences its beneficial (or negative) effects even when he is away from home: at school, at work, on vacation in another city, on a business trip. And the student sitting at the school desk is mentally and emotionally connected with his house, family and many problems that concern him with invisible threads.

However, there are certain difficulties, contradictions and shortcomings of educational influence in the family. The most common negative factors of family education that should be taken into account in the educational process are:

- inadequate influence of material factors: abundance or lack of things, superiority of material well-being over spiritual needs of a growing person, disproportion of material needs and opportunities to satisfy them, depravity and womanizing, immorality and illegality of the family economy;

- - lack of spirituality of parents, lack of desire for children's spiritual development;
- - authoritarianism or "liberalism", impunity and forgiveness;
- - immorality, the existence of an immoral style and tone of relations in the family;
- - absence of a normal psychological climate in the family;
- - fanaticism in any form;
- - pedagogical illiteracy, illegal behavior of adults.

Among the various tasks of the family, education of the young generation is undoubtedly of priority. This function includes the whole life of the family and is related to all aspects of its activity.

However, the practice of family education shows that some parents teach their children.

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